

Lignin-first fractionation of softwood lignocellulose, using a mild dimethyl carbonate and ethylene glycol organosolv process

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Abstract: Here we report on a mild lignin-first acidolysis process (140 °C, 40 min) that uses the benign solvent dimethyl carbonate (DMC) and ethylene glycol (EG) as stabilization agent/solvent in order to produce high yield of aromatic monophenols directly from softwood lignocellulose (pine, spruce, cedar, and Douglas fir) with a depolymerization efficiency of 77–98%. At optimized conditions (140 °C, 40 min, 400 wt% EG and 2 wt% H₂SO₄ to pinewood) up to 9 wt% of aromatic monophenol was produced reaching a degree of delignification in pinewood of 77%. Cellulose was also preserved as evidenced by a 85% glucose yield after enzymatic digestion. An in-depth analysis of the depolymerization oil was conducted using GC-MS, HPLC, 2D-NMR and SEC providing structural insights into lignin derived dimers and oligomers and the composition of sugars and derived molecules. Mass balance evaluation was provided.

Introduction

The development of profitable and sustainable biorefineries relies on the optimal valorization of the three major lignocellulose constituents: cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin.^[1] Among these, lignin valorization has proven to be a major bottleneck due to its complex nature and recalcitrant structure, especially upon

classical processing conditions.^[2,3] Several elegant strategies have been reported for the depolymerization of organosolv lignins,^[2,4,5] however, the obtainable monomer yields were not only dependent on the method used, but also on the original lignocellulose fractionation conditions.^[4,6–8] To overcome this, recently, attention was shifted to lignin first strategies, which accomplish the depolymerization of lignin in its native form, during the lignocellulose fractionation process.^[9] These novel strategies generally focus on the use of a heterogeneous metal catalyst and hydrogen gas.^[10–19]

Previously we have found that stabilization of reactive intermediates during acid catalyzed depolymerization of lignin leads to suppression of recondensation processes and improved aromatic monomer yield (Fig. 1 and Fig. S2).^[20] Specifically, acidolysis was studied using various lignin model compounds and organosolv lignins with TfOH or Fe(OTf)₃ as catalyst, in dioxane or toluene.^[6,8,20–22]

Trapping the so formed reactive 2-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)acetaldehyde and 2-(4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxyphenyl)acetaldehyde (G- and S-C2-aldehydes respectively) with various diols, prominently ethylene glycol, resulted in the formation of the corresponding cyclic acetals comprising either a guaiacyl (G-C2 acetal) or a syringyl (S-C2-acetal) moiety respectively (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. One of the dominant reaction pathway (C2) during acid catalyzed depolymerization of lignin with and without ethylene glycol trapping.

Figure 2. Lignin acidolysis in conjunction with stabilization of reactive intermediates with ethylene glycol to obtain G-C2-acetal. Starting from lignocellulose directly (one-step) versus starting from organosolv lignin (two-step) procedure. [a] Yield based on initial lignin content; [b] Yield based on lignin extraction efficiency.

These compounds could be produced in up to 35.5% yield from various organosolv lignin sources^[8]. The yield of the obtained products was correlated, among others, with the β -O-4' moiety content of the lignins, which strongly depended on the method of isolation.^[8] Moreover, not all the employed lignin extraction methods were efficient enough, depending on the source. Starting from softwood, first organosolv lignin was extracted with limited efficiency (33% from Cedar). The G-C2-acetal yield obtained in the next step was 17 wt%, meaning a total 2 wt% product yield compared to the lignin content of the raw biomass (Fig. 2). Also, NMR studies showed partial condensation in the final lignins as a result of the isolation procedure.^[6-8]

Therefore, we set out to investigate the application of our previously developed method to softwood lignocellulose directly, skipping the tedious lignin isolation step (Fig. 2). In fact, such strategy would not differ much from a classical lignocellulose fractionation process except the reaction conditions, catalyst, and added stabilization agent (EG) should be specifically tailored to deliver the desired monophenolic G-C2-acetal instead of organosolv lignin. One related example was reported in literature by Watanabe et al^[23] using a mixture of toluene and methanol as solvent, whereby methanol also acted as a trapping agent, and H_2SO_4 as a catalyst to produce a non-cyclic C2-acetal^[24] from Japanese cedar wood with monomer yield of approximately 5 wt% to lignin. Due to a different focus of this study in polymer chemistry, the effectiveness of the depolymerization method was not evaluated and no information regarding the quality of cellulosic residue was provided.

Through systematic investigation of multiple reaction parameters, we found a novel system that successfully integrates lignocellulose processing and lignin depolymerization in order to deliver high yield of monophenolic G-C2-acetal directly from softwood lignocellulose while maintaining cellulose susceptibility to enzyme hydrolysis as evidenced from hydrolysis studies. Although the use of softwood generally leads to lower monomer

yield compared to hardwood, mainly due to lower β -O-4' linkage content, the presence of only G-units leads to exclusively one monomer (G-C2-acetal, Fig. 2). Gratingly, we managed to replace the previously used 1,4-dioxane and toluene to the green solvent dimethyl carbonate (DMC) and the corrosive and expensive triflic acid/triflates to sulfuric acid. The superior performance of the green solvent DMC was rationalized by displaying correlations between solvent parameters and G-C2-acetal yield. An in-depth analysis of the depolymerization oil was performed to identify lignin dimers and oligomers, as well as carbohydrates or derived compounds and a good mass balance was achieved. The general applicability of the method was demonstrated on 4 different softwood species.

Results and Discussion

The two key factors necessary to obtain high yield of monophenolic products from raw lignocellulose are: a) efficient delignification and b) rapid β -O-4' bond cleavage. Since both of these steps depend on multiple factors, an extensive optimization of reaction parameters (catalyst type and amount, ethylene glycol amount, solvent, reaction time, and temperature) was carried out in order to maximize G-C2-acetal yield and at the same time maintain high cellulose quality.

C2-acetal production from pinewood: evaluation of catalysts and solvents

First, benchmark conditions previously developed for organosolv lignin depolymerization (catalyst: $\text{Fe}(\text{OTf})_3$, solvent: 1,4-dioxane) were evaluated processing pine lignocellulose in the catalyst concentration range of 0.075-0.3 mmol (Table 1, Entry 1-5) whereby 0.15 mmol were found to be the minimum requirement to obtain G-C2-acetal yield of 4.8 wt% (Table 1, Entry 3). Then H_2SO_4 , $\text{Bi}(\text{OTf})_3$, and *p*-TsOH were screened as alternatives for $\text{Fe}(\text{OTf})_3$ ^[25] (Table 1, Entry 6-8). The use of $\text{Bi}(\text{OTf})_3$ provided a

similar yield of G-C2-acetal (5.0 wt% vs 4.8 wt% for Fe(OTf)₃), while with *p*-TsOH no G-C2-acetal was obtained. Interestingly, sulfuric acid, as a much cheaper alternative, performed better than Fe(OTf)₃ with 5.7 wt% G-C2-acetal yield and therefore it was chosen for the further optimization.

Our next goal was to find greener alternatives for 1,4-dioxane that is classified as a solvent with major known issues^[26] at the same time maintaining a high product yield. Dimethoxyethane (monoglyme) and toluene performed similar to 1,4-dioxane (G-C2-acetal yield 6.1 wt% and 5.3 wt% respectively, Table 1, Entry 9 and 10) while acetone gave slightly lower yield (4.3 wt%). Very poor G-C2-acetal yield was obtained in alcohols (Table 1, Entry 12,13 and 19) as was demonstrated before for model compounds.^[20] Previously, etherification of the β-O-4' motifs at the α-OH position was reported when alcohols were used as reaction media under similar conditions.^[6] It is likely that the resulting ethers are less reactive under these conditions.^[7] Treatment of lignin with EG under acidic conditions was previously reported by Jasiukaityte-Grojzdek et al.^[27], showing EG incorporation into the lignin structure in α and γ positions of the β'-O-4 linkage, even leading to cross-linking of lignin moieties. Additionally, Ono et al.^[28] studied incorporation of EG moieties into lignin during softwood acid solvolysis to produce modified lignin, potentially applicable as amphiphilic polymer and/or functional gels.

Carbonates were identified as benign solvents for organic synthesis,^[29-31] and can be synthesized via sustainable pathways directly from CO₂.^[31] Previously these solvents have proven successful in extracting lignin from sugarcane bagasse while preserving a good cellulose quality (up to 90% glucose yield after enzymatic digestion).^[32,33] Gratifyingly, in our system, dimethyl carbonate and diethyl carbonate appeared to be outstanding solvents reaching 8.0 wt% G-C2-acetal yield (Table 1, Entry 14 and 15). Ethylene carbonate (EC) was also considered as valuable option (Table 1, Entry 18). However, the system was found to be challenging since EC would solidify on cooling down, clogging the reactor. Thus, lower boiling point carbonates were considered easier to work with.

To rationalize the role of the solvent, additional analysis was performed. It was previously demonstrated that solvent properties play a key role in solubilization of biopolymers, as well as liquid-phase reaction rates of biomass-derived compounds. Therefore, we take into account the following parameters: formation/yield of G-C2-acetal and Hildebrand solubility parameter to see the effect of the solvent solubilization properties.

Earlier studies elucidating solvent effects on biomass pretreatment and on solubility of lignins,^[34-38] employed the Hildebrand solubility parameter (δ -value)^[39]. According to the Hildebrand solubility theory, materials with similar δ -values will be able to interact with each other, resulting in solvation, miscibility, or swelling. Solvents employed in this study and their corresponding δ -values are listed in Table S3, while for lignin, δ -values can vary from 20 to 28 MPa^{0.5} depending on origin and processing history.^[40-42] As benchmark δ -value for the lignin in our study we use the value (25.8 MPa^{0.5}) previously calculated for softwood organosolv lignin by Le et al.^[43] Furthermore, δ -values for mixtures of solvents with EG (Table S3) were calculated by averaging the Hildebrand values of the individual solvents by volume.^[44] Interestingly, the δ -values for all screened mixtures were lower than that of lignin and displayed no obvious correlation with the G-C2-acetal yield, suggesting that G-C2-acetal formation

is independent of the lignin release from the lignocellulose matrix, while several factors can effect G-C2-acetal yields.

In the study of Brønsted acid catalyzed reactions the role of solvents in accelerating reaction rates has been implicated in a number of ways. It was shown that the appropriate choice of solvent can result in reduced activation energy for dehydration reactions through improved stabilization of transition state resulting from improved proton availability.^[35,45] In our case, dehydration of the α-position of the β-O-4' moiety is the first step towards the formation of the G-C2-acetal product where the acid catalyzed reaction in non-aqueous solvents proportionally depends on the relative permittivity of the solvent.^[46]

The highest G-C2-acetal yields can be obtained using solvents with low relative permittivity ($\epsilon_r < 5$) and moderate dipole moments (μ). A volcano-shaped plot (Fig. 3) of the solvent

Table 1. Catalyst and solvent screening for G-C2-acetal production in lignin-first acidolysis with EG stabilization using pinewood

Entry	Catalyst	Catalyst [mmol]	Yield G-C2-acetal [wt %]	Solvent
1	Fe(OTf) ₃	0.075	1.5	1,4-dioxane
2 ^[a]	Fe(OTf) ₃	0.075	1.3	1,4-dioxane
3	Fe(OTf) ₃	0.150	4.8	1,4-dioxane
4	Fe(OTf) ₃	0.210	4.3	1,4-dioxane
5	Fe(OTf) ₃	0.300	4.4	1,4-dioxane
6	Bi(OTf) ₃	0.150	5.0	1,4-dioxane
7	<i>p</i> -TsOH	0.150	0.0	1,4-dioxane
8	H ₂ SO ₄	0.150	5.7	1,4-dioxane
9	H ₂ SO ₄	0.150	6.1	Dimethoxyethane
10	H ₂ SO ₄	0.150	5.3	Toluene
11	H ₂ SO ₄	0.150	4.3	Acetone
12	H ₂ SO ₄	0.150	1.1	<i>t</i> -Amyl alcohol
13	H ₂ SO ₄	0.150	0.0	<i>n</i> -Butanol
14	H ₂ SO ₄	0.150	8.0	Dimethyl carbonate (DMC)
15	H ₂ SO ₄	0.150	8.0	Diethyl carbonate (DEC)
16	H ₂ SO ₄	0.150	2.0	Heptane
17	H ₂ SO ₄	0.150	2.8	GVL
18	H ₂ SO ₄	0.150	n.d. ^[b]	Ethylene carbonate
19	H ₂ SO ₄	0.150	1	Ethylene glycol

Reaction conditions: Pine lignocellulose (1.5 g), EG (0.9 mL, 66 wt% to pine), solvent (29.1 mL), 140 °C, 30 minutes (excl. 10 minutes to reach 140 °C from room temperature); G-C2-acetal yield based on GC-FID calibration curve with octadecane as internal standard and based on lignin content of pine lignocellulose; [a] 90 minutes; [b] not determined

Figure 3. Dependence of C2-acetal yield on solvent properties (dipole moment, μ and relative permittivity, ϵ_r). Aprotic solvents considered.

properties (relative permittivity and dipole moment) vs G-C2-acetal yields demonstrates that both too polar and nonpolar solvents have a degenerative effect on the G-C2-acetal yield. Likely, too polar solvents raise the acid strength leading to both condensation of native lignin and/or product decomposition while nonpolar solvents are likely ineffective at stabilizing the transition state.

Future studies in this direction could be accelerated by quantifying solvation effects in terms of initial and transition state contributions using experimental and computational methodologies, thereby elucidating the fundamental basis for predicting solvent effects and rational solvent design.

Optimization of reaction conditions for pine lignocellulose

Further reaction parameter optimization was conducted including EG to H_2SO_4 ratio, time, and temperature. Dimethyl carbonate was chosen for further optimization due to its lower boiling point (91 °C vs 126 °C for DEC), which potentially facilitates its recovery.

At first, EG content was varied in the range of 66 to 400 wt% with respect to pine lignocellulose using 0.15 mmol and 0.3 mmol H_2SO_4 (1 wt% and 2 wt% to pinewood respectively, Fig. S8). When 1 wt% H_2SO_4 was used together with 66 to 400 wt% EG, G-C2-acetal yield decreased drastically from 8 wt% to 2.7 wt%. This can be due to the presence of higher EG concentration and its incorporation into the α -position of β -O-4' motifs that leads to a less effective β -O-4' cleavage^[6]. In order to verify this, an arylglycerol β -aryl ether lignin model compound (MC) was subjected to the same conditions (DMC, 140 °C) with 4, 8, 16, and 32 equivalents of EG (Fig. S3) leading to a markedly slower cleavage reaction. With increasing EG content from 4 to 32 equivalents, the G-C2-acetal yield decreased from 40% to 10% while EG-adduct formation was favoured (Fig. S4–S7). This is in line with previously observed EG incorporation in α -position of β -O-4' motifs of lignin.^[6,7,27,28] In order to promote the β -O-4' cleavage reaction in lignin, we raised the amount of catalyst to 2 wt%. At this catalyst concentration, a constant G-C2-acetal yield (9 wt%) was seen when EG was increased from 66 wt% to 400 wt% to pinewood. Probably, α -etherification being a reversible process^[6,7], the EG-incorporated adduct became less stable in the presence of 2 wt% H_2SO_4 rendering the subsequent bond scission easier. Then, the effect of EG was studied systematically in terms of G-C2-acetal yield and degree of delignification, going

Figure 4. Degree of delignification (DD) and G-C2-acetal yield versus δ -value of solvent mixture with varying EG content of EG-DMC mixtures (Table S4). Pine lignocellulose (1.5 g), EG (0.9-8 mL, 66-590 wt% to pine), DMC (22-29.1 mL), H_2SO_4 (30 mg, 2 wt% to pinewood), 140 °C, 30 minutes (excl. 10 minutes to reach 140 °C from room temperature)

from 66 wt% to 590 wt% EG in the presence of 2 wt% H_2SO_4 (Table S4, Fig. 4). As shown, G-C2-acetal yield was constant (9 wt%) within the studied EG concentration range. However, when EG concentration was increased further to 500-590 wt%, a decrease in monomer yield to 7 wt% was observed, likely due to inefficient cleavage reaction as previously explained. Poor G-C2-acetal yield was found when pure EG was used as solvent (1.1 %)

The degree of delignification (DD) increased from 34% to 77% following the increase in EG concentration from 66 to 400 wt%, and from there remained constant up to 590 wt% (Table S4, Fig. 4). The addition of EG was previously shown to be effective for lignin removal from lignocellulose.^[47] Taking into consideration the Hildebrand solubility parameter, the δ -value of the used EG-DMC mixtures increased from 20.6 to 22.9 MPa^{0.5} as the EG fraction of the reaction mixture increased from 3 to 27 vol% (66 to 590 wt% with respect to pinewood) approaching the lignin δ -value of 25.8 MPa^{0.5}. Accordingly, the DD increased in line with the increase in δ -value of the mixtures (Fig. 4). However, when EG was maintained in the range of 66-400 wt%,

G-C2-acetal yield was independent of the degree of delignification (Fig. 4). This supports the idea that G-C2-acetal formation is independent of lignin release from the lignocellulose matrix. In fact, β -O-4' linkages are the most labile and they are likely the first to be cleaved, releasing the desired G-C2-acetal monomer. Considering our previous findings on the effect of EG concentration, we postulate that increasing the EG content to 500 and above promotes delignification but lignin is likely extracted in a more stable form (α -etherified with EG), which does not cleave in the timescale of the reaction.

Hence, 400 wt% ethylene glycol concentration was considered optimal to reach maximum DD and a G-C2-acetal yield close to theoretical maximum (98%) based on Derivatization Followed by Reductive Cleavage (DFRC) theoretical monomer yield calculations (see SI, section 1.4 and 3). Interestingly, this G-C2-acetal yield (7.6 mol% to Klason lignin) is also comparable, but slightly lower than the total monophenol yield of 10.4-8.7 mol% (to Klason lignin content), previously obtained by RCF method for the same pinewood.^[17] This slightly lower yield is expected, as this particular product is the result of the cleavage

Figure 5. Tuning the system: schematic representation of the main parameters influencing G-C2-acetal yield and degree of delignification (EG, H₂SO₄)

of a β -O-4' moiety by the C2-pathway, while the minor C3 pathway would release Hibbert ketones as additional products (Fig. 7).

Nonetheless, this method delivers G-C2-acetals generally not accessible by RCF, giving access to potentially important alternative lignin platform chemicals. Overall, the presented results were found comparable to reductive catalytic fractionation methods applied to softwood (Table S6). In fact, DD of 54–84% were reported previously with aromatic monomers yield of 9–23 wt%. Since softwood contains only G-units, selectivity to a single aromatic monomer of 86–93% was reported.^[48–50]

Subsequently, reaction time (Fig. S9) and temperature (Fig. S10) were investigated. Reaction times of longer than 30 minutes did not improve the G-C2-acetal yield. Interestingly, DD did not improve with time either. With respect to temperature, 140 °C appeared optimal since 120 °C was found to be too low to give satisfactory delignification and monomer yield (52.7% and 4.7 wt% respectively) on the other hand, 160 °C resulted in lower monomer yield likely due to decomposition of the product (6.5 wt%).

Overall, the system can be controlled by tuning the EG and H₂SO₄ content (Fig. 5). The favorable properties of the solvent DMC would facilitate the first dehydration step in acidolysis by stabilization of the formed carbocation intermediate, as previously discussed. Then, in the absence of EG or at higher acid concentration, undesired condensation reactions take place, leading to low target monomer yield. However, in the presence of EG, the G-C2 aldehyde formed upon acidolysis is stabilized in the form of its cyclic G-C2-acetal and in optimum, 400 wt% EG amount, maximum DD is reached as well. Nevertheless, α -etherification occurs when EG amount increases or H₂SO₄ is too low delivering a more stable lignin and lower yield of monophenols.

Additionally, the optimum conditions found (400 wt% EG to pinewood, 140 °C, 2 wt% H₂SO₄, 40 minutes) were applied to three softwood species (cedar, spruce, and Douglas fir) in order to expand the scope of the method (see Section 3 in SI for

characterization). Depolymerization efficiency (DE, see SI, section 1.4 and 3) was determined based on the theoretical maximum monomer yield using the DFRC method as benchmark^[51] (Table 2, see SI for calculations). Spruce and Douglas fir were found to need half of the acid content in order to perform efficient depolymerization to G-C2-acetal (Table 2, Entry 4 and 6). Importantly, the method resulted in high depolymerization efficiency (77–98%) for all tested wood species. Importantly, the obtained results were found comparable to reductive fractionation methods applied to softwood where a DE of 75–93% was reported (Table S6).^[48–50]

Table 2. Testing the generality of the method by using cedar, spruce and Douglas Fir as substrate.

Entry	Lignocellulose	G-C2-acetal yield [wt% to lignin]	DE ^[a] [%]
1	Pine	8.8	98
2	Cedar	7.1	92
3	Spruce	4.0	42
4	Spruce ^[b]	6.7	77
5	Douglas Fir	3.7	44
6	Douglas Fir ^[b]	6.7	80

Reaction conditions: lignocellulose (1.5 g), EG (5.4 mL, 400 wt% to pine), DMC (24.6 mL), H₂SO₄ (15–30 mg, 1–2 wt% to pinewood), 140 °C, time: 30 min (excl. 10 minutes to reach 140 °C from room temperature); G-C2-acetal yield based on GC-FID calibration curve with octadecane as internal standard and based on lignin content of pine lignocellulose [a] DE (Depolymerization efficiency) based on DFRC analysis (see SI, section 1.4 and 3); [b] 1 wt% H₂SO₄ to lignocellulose.

Figure 6. Fractionation of depolymerization oil in order to provide structural insights. Reaction conditions: Pine lignocellulose (1.5 g), EG (5.4 mL, 400 wt% to pine), DMC (24.6 mL), H_2SO_4 (30 mg, 2 wt% to pinewood), 140 °C, 30 minutes (excl. 10 minutes to reach 140 °C from room temperature).

Structural insights and identification of by-products.

Next, analysis of the obtained depolymerization oil was performed. To this end, an appropriate fractionation procedure was developed, the schematic representation of which is shown in Fig. 6. After filtration of the solid residues, the organic phase was extracted with water in order to separate the water-soluble carbohydrate products (aqueous phase, Fraction 2) from lignin depolymerization products (organic phase, Fraction 1). Fraction 1 was characterized in great detail as follows. After evaporation of the solvent, Fraction 1 was subjected to GC-MS analysis (before and after derivatization via silylation), HSQC and HMBC NMR as well as SEC analysis.

In the absence of silylation, the GC-MS trace (Fig. S11, black) showed G-C2-acetal as dominant signal together with traces of 2-methoxy-4-(3-methyl-5,6-dihydro-1,4-dioxin-2-yl)pheno^[52] (dioxene HB2, Fig. 7) deriving from the C3-pathway of lignin acidolysis (Fig. S2 and 7). Also, formation of acetals originating from the reactions of carbohydrates with EG could be observed.

Derivatization of the sample by silylation allowed for the detection of additional signals in the higher temperature range of the GC-MS trace, attributable to higher molecular weight compounds, mainly dimers (Fig. S11, pink). Here also, (C2-acetal-TMS) was the main component together with 2-((trimethylsilyloxy)ethyl) acetate (ethylene glycol monoacetate). These findings were also confirmed by 2D NMR analysis of the crude reaction mixture (Fig. S12 and S13).

In order to better separate possible lignin derived oligomeric products from the monomer and dimer compounds, further fractionation of Fraction 1 was necessary. Therefore Fraction 1 was additionally extracted with toluene to give toluene solubles (Fraction 3) and toluene insolubles (Fraction 4) and both fractions were subjected to size-exclusion chromatography analysis (SEC) followed by HSQC and HMBC NMR studies and GC-MS analysis after silylation.

According to SEC analysis (Fig. S15), Fraction 4 (Fig. S15, dotted black line) mainly consisted of oligomers ($M_n = 1000 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$; $M_w = 1800 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, $D=1.8$). This was also confirmed by the absence of monomers in GC-MS after silylation of Fraction 4 (Fig. S16). Fraction 4 was found to account for 31 wt% of initial lignin when gravimetrically determined. Interestingly, 2D NMR showed signals in the region of 4.9/105 ppm and 2.7/40 ppm attributable to the α and β positions of G-C2-acetal (Fig. S17 and S14). It is plausible that these signals belong to lignin oligomers bearing the stabilized acetal residue on one end after β -O-4' linkage cleavage, while the other end would represent a phenolic moiety not cleavable under these conditions. In this case, the molecular weight would include the acetal functionality. This acetal group could be further functionalized during possible valorization of the oligomeric fraction. Also, signals belonging to etherified α -position in β -O-4' motifs were found, indicating possible EG incorporation.^[53]

According to the SEC analysis, Fraction 3 (Fig. S15, dashed green line) consisted primarily of low molecular weight species and no species with molecular weight higher than $1000 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ were found. Indeed, when this fraction was subjected to silylation (Fig. S18), G-C2-acetal was shown to be the major product. Analysis of oligomeric fragments was performed based on GC-MS fragmentation patterns and previously reported data.^[8,22] Based on combined data from NMR and GC-MS analysis (SI for GC-MS fragmentation details, section 7.3) we suggest the presence of structures related to Hibbert's ketones (C3-pathway of β -O-4' cleavage, Fig. 7, S20, S19) and dimeric species (various pathways from β -O-4'/ β -5 units, Fig. 7 and S21), consistently with previous literature.^[8,22] Due to the presence of C_α/H_α and C_β/H_β signals, which appeared analogue to the ones belonging to C2-acetal (SI, Fig. S22-S23, Fig. S14 for G-C2-acetal reference, $C_\alpha/H_\alpha=C1$, $C_\beta/H_\beta=C2$) it is reasonable to propose structures such as P2 or P7, as also reported previously by Lahive et al.^[22]

Figure 7. Proposed structures for lignin derived monomers and dimers based on GC-MS and 2D-NMR analysis (blue: $\beta\text{-O-4'}$ moiety, C2 and C3 pathway; green/red: $\beta\text{-5'}/\beta\text{-O-4'}$ unit, combination of C2 and C3 pathways) in accordance with literature data^[22].

The aqueous phase (*Fraction 2*) was subjected to HSQC NMR analysis, SEC and GC-MS analysis, following derivatization via acetylation procedure. According to SEC analysis, *Fraction 2* mainly consisted of low molecular weight sugars and EG (Fig. S24) and HSQC NMR indicated the presence of carbohydrates (Fig. S25). Hence, we focused on the anomeric carbon region considered as the fingerprint region for carbohydrate derivatives. In fact, previous work has shown that during lignocellulose fractionation in butanol, the anomeric carbons in glucose and xylose displayed a characteristic shift compared to native glucose and xylose.^[6,53] In order to understand whether modification at the anomeric carbon occurred in our system, native hemicellulose monomers xylose and mannose (usually in a 1:3 ratio xylose to mannose in pinewood^[54]) and cellulose monomer glucose were tested under the previously established reaction conditions (Fig. 8). Indeed, a modification of the native monomers at the anomeric carbon by both EG and methanol (deriving from partial DMC decomposition, Fig. 8) was seen by combined HSQC and HMBC NMR experiments (Fig. S27, S32 and S35). Furthermore, NMR signals detected in *Fraction 2* were found to match the model reactions of glucose, xylose, and mannose (Fig. S28, S33 and S36). The presence of these modified sugars in *Fraction 2* was also suggested by GC-MS analysis (Fig. S37). To conclude, part of the carbohydrates were hydrolyzed during the biomass treatment resulting in xylose, mannose, and glucose modified by methanol or EG. EG-modification of xylose was reported before by Doherty et al.^[32] when treating sugarcane bagasse in a system consisting of EC/EG/ H_2SO_4 .

Next, we took a closer look at the possible reactivity of the solvent, DMC in our system. When the crude depolymerization mixture was analyzed by 2D NMR, as previously mentioned, ethylene carbonate was detected, indicating that DMC and ethylene glycol are partially reacting, releasing methanol^[55] (Fig. 8). In our system, 2.2% of the original DMC was converted to ethylene carbonate, as quantified by GC-FID measurement. EG oligomerization products were also detected, additionally contributing to solvent loss, even though their precise quantification was not possible. In order to further understand the role of DMC in transformation of carbohydrates under our established conditions, a test reaction with glucose was performed (DMC, H_2SO_4 , 140 °C, 20 minutes) in the absence of EG, showing only native glucose by NMR analysis (Fig. S30). However, considering that DMC partially reacts with EG to release methanol as previously discussed, in our system, sugars can undergo Fischer glycosidation both with EG as well as methanol at the anomeric carbon (Fig. 8). Quantification of the sugars in the aqueous phase (*Fraction 2*) by HPLC analysis found a combined mannose and xylose yield of 29.8% compared to initial hemicellulose and a glucose yield of 16.3% to initial cellulose. Since approximately 70% of purified cellulose in softwood was found to be crystalline^[56] it is plausible that the sugar monomers originate mainly from the amorphous fraction of carbohydrates, which were partially dissolved and hydrolysed during our fractionation process. As mentioned, EG was found to be a reactive component in the system. The amount of unreacted EG present in the system (*Fraction 2*) was calculated based on HPLC

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analysis resulting in a final 52.4% of unreacted EG to initial EG. An overview of the EG distribution in the different fractions is given in Table S7.

Figure 8. Compositional study of the reaction liquor: Partial transformation of DMC with EG to yield EC and methanol. Subsequent methanol and ethylene glycol incorporation into glucose via the Fischer glycosidation.

Pulp analysis and enzymatic digestion

The carbohydrate-rich solid residues (Fig. 6) obtained from experiments using different amount of EG at constant G-C2-acetal yield (0, 66, 300, 400 wt% to pinewood) were characterized in terms of lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose content (Table S5) and tested for enzymatic digestibility. Interestingly, EG was also found in the reaction mixture after hydrolysis with sulfuric acid indicating its incorporation into carbohydrates.

The EG concentration was broadly constant (0.130-0.154 wt% relative to the solid residue) and independent of the amount of the EG used for the parent fractionation experiment (66 to 400 wt%), thus it seems very likely that a saturation of carbohydrates' reactive groups with EG takes place. In fact, following our previous findings on the composition of *Fraction 2*, EG should also be able to react with the anomeric carbon of polysaccharides according to the Fischer glycosylation mechanism. The incorporation of EG in the solid residues contributes to EG solvent loss (Table S5 and S7).

The characterized dry residual pulps (0, 66, 300 and 400 wt% EG to pinewood) were used to screen the enzymatic digestibility (Fig. S38), where the residue treated with the highest EG amount (400 wt%) provided the highest glucose yield (28.8%). This is reasonable given it had the lowest lignin content (13.4%) since lignin is known to deactivate enzymes^[67]. However, subjecting dry pulps to enzymatic digestion faces the problem that the surface is less accessible for the enzyme. Thus, enzymatic hydrolysis of the freshly treated feedstock using 400 wt% EG was also performed to result in maximum glucose yield of 84.7%, comparable with previous results reported on residual pulp from lignin extraction under similar conditions.^[6,58] Due to the EG incorporation in the solid residue, the fresh pulp was tested for enzymatic digestion after EG removal via hydrolysis with aqueous sulfuric acid in order to have "free" cellulose available (SI, section 1.6). No difference in glucose yield was observed after 72 hours

enzymatic digestion when EG was hydrolyzed prior to experiment. This indicates that EG incorporation into carbohydrates has negligible effect on the activity of the enzymes (Fig. S39).

Mass balance at optimized conditions

The mass balance was evaluated using results obtained under optimized conditions (Fig. 8). Lignin was converted to a single monophenolic product (G-C2-acetal) in 9 wt% yield (**Fraction 3**), while 31 wt% of lignin ended up as lignin-derived oligomers (**Fraction 4**) and around 23 wt% of lignin remained in the solid residue. This shows that delignification should be improved to better exploit lignin. Hemicellulose was preserved in almost 52% of its initial content. Of which, 30% was isolated as a water solution and 22% remained in the solid residue. Additionally, sugar derivatives found in the organic phase most likely stem from hemicellulose. Cellulose also underwent partial dissolution, since the water phase was found to contain 16% of initial cellulose as glucose derivatives. The main part of cellulose, almost 72%, stayed in the solid residue. The solid residue was converted to glucose in 85% yield. Overall, this signifies 77% cellulose conversion. Taking into account the initial biomass composition and the yields of all the fractions, 56% of the lignocellulose was valorized.

Conclusion

A mild 'lignin first' process using sulfuric acid as catalyst and ethylene glycol as stabilization agent in the green solvent DMC was developed. Overall, high lignin depolymerization efficiency to G-C2-acetal was reached without the need for lignin isolation. A high aromatic monomer yield of 77-98% (based on DFRC) was achieved. The relationship between G-C2-acetal yield and solvent parameters was investigated, showing that solvents with low relative permittivity ($\epsilon_r < 5$) and moderate dipole moments (μ) are most beneficial.

Figure 9. Product distribution, including mass balance for lignin and carbohydrates. Numbers are reported as percent to pinewood. Optimized

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reaction conditions: Pine lignocellulose (1.5 g), EG (5.4 mL, 400 wt% to pine), DMC (24.6 mL), H₂SO₄ (30 mg, 2 wt% to pinewood), 140 °C, 30 minutes (excl. 10 minutes to reach 140 °C from room temperature)

The system was found to be tunable depending on EG and catalyst content resulting in an EG optimum of 400 wt% (to pine wood), which maximized both delignification and G-C2-acetal yield. Furthermore, deep characterization of the depolymerization oil was performed, proposing structures for aromatic dimers and identification of modified sugars dissolved in the liquor.

A partial loss of DMC due to reaction with EG was detected but the effect of this on downstream processing still has to be evaluated.

In summary, the method delivers a promising single aromatic compound (G-C2-acetal) as well as specific dimers and acetal-functionalized oligomers that can be potentially used for the manufacture of various bio-based products. One such area could be polymer chemistry, as previously reported by Watanabe et al for their monophenolic acetal product.^[24]

Notably, the process allows for effective fractionation of softwood biomass maintaining cellulose as evidenced by a glucose yield of 84.7% after enzymatic hydrolysis. In terms of mass balance, a total glucose yield of 87.8% was reached together with 51.7% of hemicellulose and 63.8% of lignin. As mentioned, softwood delivers typically low yield of aromatic monomers, albeit with high selectivity. Thus, the use of hardwood in order to get higher yield of S- and G-C2-acetals will be subject of future studies.

Experimental Section

General procedure for lignin first acidolysis in conjunction with EG stabilization

In a typical experiment, a 100 mL Parr reactor (material: Alloy 20; maximum temperature: 350 °C; maximum pressure: 200 bar) with glass insert was charged with 1.500 g lignocellulose, 0.015 g octadecane as an internal standard (0.50 mL of a stock solution in DMC 0.03 g·mL⁻¹), 5.4 mL ethylene glycol as stabilization agent (400 wt% to pinewood), 24.6 mL DMC as solvent and 30 mg sulfuric acid (1.6 mL of a stock solution in DMC 0.019 g·mL⁻¹, 2 wt% to pinewood). After sealing the reactor, the mixture was heated to 140 °C with a heating rate of 12 °C·min⁻¹ under vigorous stirring. After cooling 10 minutes with ice-bath, 1 mL of reaction mixture was filtered through celite and used for GC-FID or GC-MS analysis or both. The carbohydrate-rich solid residue (pulp) was collected via filtration and washed either with only acetone (20 mL) and dried at RT (dry pulp) or acetone (20 mL) and then water (20 mL) and kept wet (fresh pulp) for enzymatic digestion.

Volatile products analysis and characterization

The liquid phase was analyzed by a Shimadzu GC-2014 equipped with a FID detector using helium as a carrier gas. Standard settings: 1 µL injection (260 °C), split ratio 50:1, helium flow 0.95 mL·min⁻¹. The GC apparatus was equipped with a HP5 column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm). The following temperature profile was used: 5 min 60 °C isotherm followed by a 10 °C·min⁻¹ ramp for 20 minutes to 260 °C. Detector temperature was 260 °C. The quantification of G-C2-acetal was based on a calibration curve performed using G-C2-acetal synthesized and purified via a modified reported procedure^[59] versus an internal standard (octadecane). The calibration curve was used as follows:

$$m_{G-C2-acetal} = \left(\frac{Area_{G-C2-acetal}}{Area_{octadecane}} \times 2,5386 \right) \times m_{octadecane} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

G-C2-acetal yield was calculated as follows (wt% to lignin content):

$$Yield_{G-C2-acetal} = \frac{m_{G-C2-acetal}}{m_{biomass} \cdot W_{lignin}^{W_{extractives}} \text{ at } 105^\circ\text{C}} \times 100\% \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

The calculated G-C2-acetal yield includes the weight added by EG.

The liquid phase was analyzed by Shimadzu GC-MS equipped with a HP5 column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm) using the same method as described for GC-FID.

Pinewood fractionation procedure

In order to have additional insight into the remaining components in the oil residue, a fractionation procedure was applied at optimized conditions (Fig. 6). After filtering off the residual carbohydrate-rich solid, 15 mL of buffer solution K₂HPO₄/KH₂PO₄ pH = 8 was added to the DMC phase (typically 30 mL) to neutralize the catalyst and extract water soluble compounds and EG. DCM (5 mL) was added to help the separation. Two fractions were obtained: *Fraction 1* consisting of the organic phase and *Fraction 2* - the aqueous phase. *Fraction 1* was characterized by GC-MS (before and after silylation), HSQC/HMBC NMR, SEC analysis. After characterization, *Fraction 1* was extracted with toluene (5 mL x 3) resulting in 2 additional fractions (*Fraction 3*: toluene soluble, *Fraction 4*: toluene insoluble) which were analyzed by the same techniques. *Fraction 2* was characterized by HSQC/HMBC NMR and GC-MS analysis after acetylation. In order to quantify carbohydrates, *Fraction 2* (aqueous phase) was subjected to hydrolysis to release native glucose, xylose, and mannose (5 wt% aqueous H₂SO₄, 120 °C, 1 h).

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Keywords: lignin • dimethyl-carbonate • stabilization of intermediates • mild depolymerization • acidolysis

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Entry for the Table of Contents

A mild 'lignin first' process using sulfuric acid as catalyst and ethylene glycol as stabilization agent in the benign solvent DMC was developed to produce a single monophenolic product and ~~good quality~~ good quality cellulose yielding 85% glucose on enzymatic hydrolysis from pine lignocellulose.

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